

COST AND PROFITABILITY OF DIFFERENT LEVEL OF JAGGERY (GUR) PRODUCTION IN SITAPUR DISTRICT OF UTTAR PRADESH

Vikash Mishra*¹, Shivraj Singh Dhakad*², Dr. R.K. Kulshreshtha*³,
Pooja Chahar*⁴, Aarti Kumari*⁵

*^{1,2,4,5}M.Sc.(Ag) Agricultural Economics, Department Of Agricultural Economics, Rbs College
Bichpuri, Agra (U.P.), India.

*³Assistant Professor, Department Of Agricultural Economics, Rbs College Bichpuri, Agra (U.P.), India.

ABSTRACT

Sugarcane is the main source of sugar (80%) globally and holds a prominent position as a cash crop. It is one of the main crops of earning foreign exchange. The sugar juice is used for making white sugar, brown sugar (khandsari) and jaggery (gur). The main by-products of sugarcane industry are bagasses and molasses. There are two distinct agro-climatic regions of sugarcane cultivation in India, viz., tropical and subtropical. Tropical region has about 45% area and contributes 55% of the total sugarcane production in the country. Thus, subtropical region accounts for 55% area and shares 45% of total production of sugarcane. Jaggery is the natural sweetener which is prepared by sugarcane juice. It is available in solid, liquid and powder form. Jaggery is one of the ancient sweetening agent and is an integral part of the rural diet in many countries. The opinions of respondents were taken to know the production constraints of Gur (Jaggery) production with the consideration of different parameters. As far as age group was concerned, 62.50 percent respondents having the age of 18 to 50 year, 20.312 percent fall under up to 18 year and 17.187 percent fall under above 50 year age group. Data shows that the total expenses under gur production as increased size group decreases and the difference between 3rd (71966.44), 2nd (49957.36), and 1st (28050.90) groups. It revealed from the table that on an average net profit per tonne was estimated to be Rs.13389.44. Among the group, more profit i.e. Rs. 23132.40 per tonne gained by 3rd group respondent than the 2nd Rs. 13421.16 and 1st group Rs. 3614.72 respondent, although the difference was not much which shows that there is less role of scale of operation in the study.

Keywords: Sugarcane, Jaggery (Gur), Natural Sweetener, Respondents.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sugarcane is the main source of sugar (80%) globally and holds a prominent position as a cash crop. It is one of the main crops of earning foreign exchange. The sugar juice is used for making white sugar, brown sugar (khandsari) and Gur (Jaggery)[9]. The country had produced 28.1 million tonnes of sugar in the 2014-15 marketing year (October-September). There is consistently increase in sugarcane area production and productivity after independence. However during 2015-16 the Maharashtra state witnessed the severe drought which affected sugarcane and sugar production adversely and national sugar production declined to the level of about 25.10 million tonnes. There are 716 installed sugar factories (Co-operative-326, Private-347 & Public-43) in the country as on 31.01.2016, with crushing capacity to produce about 33 million tonnes sugar. Thus fluctuating trends in sugar production requires main focus on development of climate resilient technologies to sustain the crop productivity as well as sugar production. Sugarcane is one of the most important agro-industrial crops in our country. Sugarcane has mainly used for the purpose of three processed products viz. Sugar, Jaggery and Khandsari. Sugarcane is a renewable natural agricultural resource. The main byproducts of sugarcane industry are used for bagasse and molasses and bagasse is mainly used as fuel. It is also used for production of compressed fiber board, paper, plastics and furfural. Molasses is used in distilleries for the manufacture of ethyl alcohol, butyl alcohol, citric acid etc. Gur is the natural sweetener which is prepared by sugarcane juice. It is available in solid, liquid and powder form. Jaggery is one of the ancient sweetening agent and is an integral part of the rural diet in many countries. It is one of the most important sweeteners in India. Gur is a traditional unrefined non - centrifugal sugar consumed in Asia, Africa, Latin America and Caribbean [7]. Although labeled as the poor man's sugar, most Indians consume Gur in as such form or the other. Gur is a good source of minerals like Calcium, Iron, Phosphorous, Sodium, manganese, Vitamins and Protein. Gur is known to produce heat and give instant energy to a human body. India is a major Gur producing country in the world it

contributes about 58 percent gur production in the world. Gur industry is very popular in Uttar Pradesh it contributes about 11 percent Gur (Jaggery) production in India. The shape and size of Gur production vary from place to place. In U.P Gur is produced in different shapes and size like Basket, Laddoo, Panser, Khurpa and Rascutt. Gur is mostly manufactured by sugarcane farmers on a small scale using 3 to 4 roller cane crusher and open pan juice concentration furnace. These crushers extracted only 50-60 percent juice. The rest 20-25 percent lost due to poor extraction and is burn with bagasse as fuel. Jaggery/gur production is about 7-10 million per annum, while its per capita consumption is about 5 kg. The importance of jaggery is well known due to its great nutritive and medicinal value. Gur production is one of the important and regular sources of income specially in Sitapur district. In Sitapur district mostly farmers are involved in Gur production along with farming.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study is based on the primary data. The primary data were obtained from selected respondents. The accuracy of results obtained under the study depends largely upon the consistency of primary data. The primary data which were collected for the study pertain to the agricultural year 2020-21 The farmer do not keep any systematic record with them and providing information based on the recall their memory. Thus, there is possibility of certain bias to enter in the present study. The factor which are in the control of farmer and contributed significantly towards the marketed surplus were included in the study. Jurisdiction of the present study was only Sitapur district of Uttar Pradesh and to conduct the research study with 15 Gur (Jaggery) manufacturers/ sample respondents of different categories were interviewed from the selected villages of Maholi block of Sitapur district of Uttar Pradesh. Therefore result, obtained from thesis may not be generalized in or in whole district Sitapur district of Uttar Pradesh was selected purposively for the study purpose. Sitapur district having 19 block namely-Ailiya, Behta, Biswan, Gondlmau, Hargaon, Kasmanda, Khairabad, Laharpur, Machhrehta, Mahmudabad, Maholi, Misrikh, Pahala, Parsendi, Pisawan, Rampur Mathura, Reusa, Sakran, and Sidhau. Out of which only one block namely Maholi was selected on the basis of maximum Gur production. After selection of block a list of gur producing villages were prepared and out of which 6 villages namely-Dewaria, Khamaria, Adwari, Hazipur, Jogiyakheda, Hardaspur were selected on the basis of same criteria. The period of study pertains to the year 2020-2021 (October 2020 to March 2021). After selection of villages, a list of gur producing/manufacturing unit were prepared and further divided in to three groups on the basis of level of gur production i.e. 1st group (100-300 tons), 2nd group (301-500) and 3rd group (above 500 tons). From each group 5 producing/manufacturing units were selected randomly. Thus total 15 Gur producing/manufacturing units/ respondents were considered.

III. CONCLUSION

1. Total expenses on Gur production:

For gur manufacturing, total expenses (cost) are divided in to two parts i.e. direct cost (material cost, fuel and electric charges, and labour cost) and indirect cost (depreciation, etc.) and details are provided in Table-1. Data shows that the total expenses under gur production as increased size group decreases and the difference between 1st (28050.90), 2nd (49957.36), and 3rd (71966.44) group. The findings are similar in [10].

2. Cost of gur production per day:

The per day cost and return on gur production was also estimated, to know the per day profit. The details about per day cost of gur production are given in Table-5. Regarding expenses on material, fuel , electric charges and human labour were observer positive relationship with size group as it may be due to different level of the quantity of gur production has increasing order with size group. On an average the total expenses on material, electric, fuel and human labour was estimated to be Rs.27688.77, 49144.90 and 70954.61 per day for 1st, 2nd and 3rd group respectively. Overall the average amount of Rs. 49263.75 was required to purchase the raw material and expenses on human labour for per day gur production. The Findings are in line with the findings of [8].

3. Direct and indirect cost:

The direct cost includes material and human labour cost and under indirect cost the items like tax, insurance and depreciation of land and building and assets etc. The details about group wise direct and indirect cost are

given in Table-2. Data shows that the total expenses under gur production as increased size group decreases and the difference between 1st (27989.56), 2nd (49203.56), and 3rd (70994.51) group. Overall the average amount of Rs. 49395.87 per day gur production. [4][6] recorded similar instability in the production.

4. Profit of gur production (per day):

On the basis of per day gross expenses and gross income, net profit was also estimated and have been provided in Table-3. The net profit per day was observed in increasing order with the size group, it may be due to variation in level of gur production under different group. It was found to be Rs. 3577.61, Rs. 12495.75 and Rs. 21828.54 for 1st, 2nd and 3rd group respectively. On an average per day profit was estimated to be Rs. 12633.96 in the study area. Thus it could be concluded that profit can be increased by increasing the level of gur production by the respondents in the study area. The findings are in same with the findings of [1] [5].

5. Overall Profit from gur production:

The per ton, per day and per season (shift) net profit were estimated and details are presented in Table-4. It revealed from the table that per ton profit was found more under 3rd group than 2nd and 1st group respondents. The same pattern was observed in per day and per season profit as the case of per ton profit. Per season indicates one shift which includes from cane- crushing to packing operation of gur production and average operating day's was 180 in operating day's among the group was at par. The level of gur production was found in increasing order with size groups it may be due different level of resources for gur production. So If respondent involved in gur production in 180 operating day with the target of 100 tonnes gur production then he may be gained an amount of Rs. 223152 as net profit in one shift or per season. It is also mention that respondents involved in gur manufacturing along with farming which shows that they are depend on only gur production business in the study area. Accordingly we can estimate the net profit with level of gur production. Overall it could be concluded that business of gur production is the profitable business and there is chance of enhancing the profit with the level of gur production involved from 100 tonne with in operating day's (180) in the study area. So there is lot of scope to increase the profit from gur production in the study area. The findings are in similarities with the findings of [2][3].

Table-1: Per tonne total expenses on Gur production

Group	Direct cost (Rs.)			Indirect cost (Rs.)	Total cost (Rs.)
	Total material cost(In Rs.)	Total Machine charge(Rs.)	Total labour cost (Rs.)	Depreciation of Assets 10%	
I	21657.50	2340	3752	301.40	28050.90
II	41237.60	3620	5040	59.76	49957.36
III	60326.00	4880	6720	40.44	71966.44
Overall	41073.70	3613.33	5170.66	133.80	49991.55

Table-2: Direct and indirect cost for gur production (per day)

Group	Direct cost (Rs.)			Indirect cost (Rs.)	Total cost (Rs.)
	Total material cost	Total human labour cost	Total cost (Rs.)		
I	23944.28	3744.49	27688.77	300.79	27989.56
II	44180.50	4964.40	49144.90	58.86	49203.56
III	64324.21	6630.40	70954.61	39.90	70994.51
Overall	44149.66	5113.09	49262.75	133.18	49395.87

Table-3: Gross income per day Gur production

Operating day's	Per day production	Gross income in rupees	Price per tonne	Gross income per day
180	0.998	5693480	31630.44	31567.17
180	1.97	11275040	31319.55	61699.51
180	2.96	16933940	31359.14	92823.05
Over all	1.97	11300820	31436.37	62029.91

Table-4: Profit of Gur Production (per day)

Group	Gross income	Total expenses (Gross expenses)	Net profit
I	31567.17	27989.56	3577.61
II	61699.51	49203.76	12495.75
III	92823.05	70994.51	21828.54
Overall	62029.91	49395.94	12633.96

Table-5: Cost of Gur production (per day)

Group	Gur production (tonne)	Sugarcane (quintal)		Okra (kg)		Castor oil (liter)		Hydro (kg)	Diesel charges (Rs.)	Electricity charges (Rs.)	Labour cost (Rs.)
		Qty	Value (Rs.)	Qty	Value	Qty	value				
I	0.998	83.42	20855	3.99	239.40	1.48	298	0.998	219.56	2335.32	3744.49
II	1.97	163.35	39180	6.89	413.40	2.94	588	1.97	433.40	3565.7	4964.40
III	2.96	248.81	54226.3	10.83	649.80	4.91	982	2.96	651.20	4814.91	6630.40
Overall	1.97	165.16	39087.1	7.23	434.20	3.11	622.66	1.97	434.72	3571.97	5113.09

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The study was supported by Department of Agricultural Economics, RBS College Bichpuri, Agra (Uttar Pradesh). The authors are highly grateful to the department for providing all necessary materials to carry out the present study and for providing the genotypes.

IV. REFERENCES

- [1] Deokate. T.B. and Yadav J.P. (2010) Economic review of Sugarcane by – product (jaggery) in Maharashtra.Cooperative Sugar , 41 (5) : 47-50 .
- [2] Kallappa, M.A. (2011) Production and marketing of jaggery in north Karnataka- An economic analysis Ph.D. Thesis (Unpublished) submitted to Agricultural University , Dharwad , Karnataka , 86-107.
- [3] Kumbhar YS. 2016. Study on Gur (jaggery) industry. International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology 3(2):590-594.
- [4] Lohar, N.S. and Babar V.S. (2003) Economics of production and marketing of jaggery in Kolhapur district. AGRESCO REPORT , (Unpublished) submitted to MPKV , Rahurt : 41-66 .
- [5] Narendra Mohan and Agarwal Anushka , (2020) New ventures of value addition in jaggery processing for a dynamic sugar industry . International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology, 9 (1): 291-294.
- [6] Rao , K.P.C. and Ravikumar. K.N. , (2005) Production and marketing of jaggery in India with reference to Andhra Pradesh. Agricultural Marketing , 47 (4) : 39-43 .

- [7] Singh G. 2013. An Empirical study of Economic of sugarcane Cultivation and Processing based Farming in Uttar Pradesh. Sky Journal of Agricultural Research 2(1):7-19.
- [8] Singh, J.P. (2012) Cost and Return Analysis of Sugarcane: A Case Study in Tamilnadu. Southern India Manage Extension Research Review, 3 (2): 1-13.
- [9] Umarani S. 2014. A study on the Problem and Prospects of the Farmers Cultivation and Marketing of Sugarcane. International Journal of Business and Administration Research Review 7(1):177-188.
- [10] Varute, A.B. (2006) Economics of Production and Marketing of Jaggery in Kolhapur District M.sc. (AGRI) thesis (unpublished) submitted to Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri.45.